

1 Platelet Interactions Drive Cisplatin Resistance and 2 Enhance Clonogenicity in Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer

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53 **SUMMARY**

54 Platelets play a crucial role in cancer progression and metastasis^{1,2}. Recent studies
55 have uncovered a complex bidirectional interaction between tumor cells and
56 platelets, involving the exchange of biomolecules and signalling factors³. This
57 crosstalk has been implicated in various aspects of cancer biology, including tumor
58 growth, and immune evasion⁴. However, the specific mechanisms by which platelets
59 contribute to chemoresistance in non-small cell lung cancer remain poorly
60 understood. Here we show that platelet-tumor cell interactions significantly enhance
61 the resistance of non-small cell lung cancer cells to cisplatin treatment. Using co-
62 culture systems and transcriptomic analyses, we demonstrate that platelet exposure
63 reduces apoptosis and increases proliferation and clonogenicity capability in lung
64 cancer cells treated with cisplatin. Our findings reveal substantial changes in gene
65 expression profiles of platelet-exposed cancer cells, with significant upregulation of
66 PI3K-AKT, NF-kappa B, TNF and apoptosis-related pathways. These alterations
67 provide insight into the molecular mechanisms underlying platelet-mediated
68 chemoresistance. This study highlights the potential of targeting platelet-tumor
69 interactions as a novel strategy to enhance the efficacy of chemotherapy in lung
70 cancer⁵. By elucidating the behavioural and transcriptomic changes induced by
71 platelet exposure, our work evidence the critical role of platelets in cancer biology at
72 the molecular and signalling level.

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87

88 **ABSTRACT**

89 Platelets are pivotal in tumor progression, dissemination, and metastasis in non-small
90 cell lung cancer (NSCLC). Recent investigations have revealed a complex,
91 bidirectional crosstalk between tumor cells and platelets involving the transfer of
92 biomolecules between these cellular entities. To elucidate the potential role of this
93 interaction in promoting tumor cell chemoresistance, we conducted functional and
94 transcriptomic analyses on co-cultures of non-small cell lung cancer cells and
95 platelets treated or not with cisplatin after this interaction with platelets.
96 Our results showed a statistically significant decrease in apoptosis and increased
97 proliferation in lung cancer cells co-cultured with platelets under cisplatin treatment.
98 Additionally, platelet-exposed tumor cells exhibited an enhanced ability to form
99 single-cell colonies, indicating increased clonogenic potential. Transcriptomic
100 analysis revealed substantial changes in gene expression in the platelet-exposed

101 cells, with several vital genes differentially expressed. Pathway enrichment analysis
102 identified significant upregulation of the PI3K-AKT, NF-kappa B, and apoptosis-
103 related pathways following platelet interaction. This study uncovers novel insights into
104 the behavioural and transcriptomic alterations induced by platelet interactions in the
105 presence of cisplatin, shedding light on mechanisms driving platelet-mediated
106 chemoresistance and highlighting platelets as a potential therapeutic target to
107 enhance NSCLC treatment efficacy.

108

109 **KEYWORDS.** Non-small cell lung cancer, Platelets, Platelet-tumor cell interactions,
110 Cisplatin, Transcriptomic analysis.

111

112 **INTRODUCTION**

113 Non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) accounts for 85% of all lung cancer cases
114 globally, including adenocarcinoma and squamous cell carcinoma histological
115 subtypes¹. Despite advancements in treatment such as surgery, chemotherapy,
116 targeted therapies, and immunotherapies, NSCLC continues to be a leading cause of
117 cancer-related deaths², responsible for 1.8 million deaths (18%) in 2022³. The
118 prognosis remains poor due to high metastasis and recurrence rates, with a five-year
119 survival rate of 20%, largely dependent on the stage at diagnosis³.

120 Recent advances in genomics⁴, transcriptomics⁵, and proteomics⁶ have expanded
121 our understanding of NSCLC biology, particularly the interactions between NSCLC
122 and immune cell types such as platelets^{7,8}. However, more research is needed to
123 unravel the complex bidirectional interaction between platelets and tumor cells. On
124 the one hand, platelets respond locally and systematically to cancer by absorbing
125 proteins, nucleic acids, vesicles, and free particles from tumor cells, thereby altering

126 their RNA and protein profiles; then, these “tumor-educated platelets” (TEPs)^{9,10} can
127 serve as predictive and prognostic biomarkers in oncology^{8,11}. On the other hand,
128 platelets also transfer biomolecules to tumor cells; then these “platelet-educated
129 tumor cells” (PETs)¹² undergo phenotypic, genetic, and functional changes that
130 promote migration, dissemination, survival, and immune evasion^{12–14}.

131 Tumor cell survival and resistance to immune cell attacks are critical for metastasis
132 development¹⁵. However, the genetic pathways enabling this immune evasion to
133 remain unclear. And also, how interactions between immune cells and cancer cells
134 contribute to resistance against targeted therapies and chemotherapy remains poorly
135 understood¹⁶. While targeted therapies based on actionable molecular biomarkers
136 have led to the approval of eight biomarkers for advanced NSCLC, such as EGFR
137 mutations (12-15%), ALK fusions (2-5%), ROS1 fusions (1-2%), BRAF V600
138 mutations (2-4%), NTRK fusions (less than 1%), RET fusions (1-3%), KRASG12C
139 mutations (26-41%), and METex14 mutations (1-3%)¹⁷, these therapies are limited to
140 patients with specific genetic profiles, representing less than 40% of the NSCLC
141 population. As a result, non-specific chemotherapies, like cisplatin, are frequently
142 employed, often in combination with targeted therapies, to enhance their
143 effectiveness^{18,19}. Cisplatin, a platinum-based alkylating agent, is widely used in
144 chemotherapy for several cancers, including sarcomas, carcinomas, lymphomas, and
145 germ-cell tumors. It induces apoptosis by binding to cellular DNA²⁰. However,
146 acquired resistance mechanisms and dose-limiting toxicities often compromise its
147 efficacy²¹. Ongoing research seeks to refine cisplatin therapy, overcome these
148 limitations, and improve patient outcomes.

149 This study aims to elucidate the functional and transcriptomic changes induced by
150 platelet interactions in cisplatin-treated NSCLC cells. We employed in vitro co-culture

151 systems, functional assays, and transcriptomic sequencing to investigate how
152 platelet-derived factors influence tumor cell survival, proliferation, and clonogenic
153 potential post-cisplatin exposure. Additionally, we sought to identify critical molecular
154 pathways and gene expression signatures linked to platelet-mediated
155 chemoresistance, advancing our understanding of how platelet-tumor cell crosstalk
156 contributes to treatment resistance.

157

158 RESULTS

159 1- Platelet co-culture decreases cisplatin sensitivity in A549 and H1299 160 lung cancer cell lines.

161 To evaluate the protective effect of platelets against conventional chemotherapy to
162 treat NSCLC, we co-cultured A549 and H1299 cell lines with platelets in the presence
163 of cisplatin. Our results revealed that platelet co-culture significantly increased the
164 cisplatin concentration required to reach the IC₅₀ in both cell lines. Specifically, the
165 IC₅₀ for the A549 cell line increased to 11.965 μ M in the presence of platelets,
166 compared to 7.230 μ M without platelets (**Fig. 1A**). Similarly, the IC₅₀ for the H1299
167 cell line rose to 16.284 μ M with platelets, compared to 11.952 μ M without them (**Fig.**
168 **1B**).

169

170 **Figure 1.** Impact of platelets on cisplatin IC50 in cell lines.

171 **A)** IC50 values of cisplatin following a 48 hour-treatment in A549 cells either as a

172 control or co-culture with platelets. **B)** IC50 values of cisplatin after a 48 hour-

173 treatment in H1299 cell line control or co-culture with platelets.

174 Abbreviation: PLT: platelets, CisPt: cisplatin, IC50: half maximal inhibitory

175 concentration.

176

177 **2- Platelets reduce cisplatin-induced apoptosis and enhance cell**
178 **proliferation of lung cancer cells.**

179 The observed reduction in cisplatin sensitivity may be attributed to several factors,

180 including the antiapoptotic influence of platelets. To explore this, we performed cell

181 death and apoptosis assays in A549 and H1299 cell lines 24 hours after treatment

182 with cisplatin at their respective IC50 concentrations. In the A549 cell line, platelets

183 significantly reduced cisplatin-induced apoptosis, with only 9.65% apoptotic cells

184 compared to 15.47 % in the absence of platelets ($p < 0.05$) (**Fig. 2A**). Similarly, co-

185 culturing H1299 cells with platelets resulted in a marked decrease in apoptosis, with

186 11.80% apoptotic cells versus 21.86% without platelets (**Fig. 2B**). In both cell lines,

187 no significant differences were found in necrotic cell death with or without platelets in

188 both cell lines (Fig 2A and Fig 2B). Additionally, no significant differences were noted

189 in untreated conditions, regardless of the presence of platelets in either cell line.

190 Platelets could also influence the proliferative capacity of lung tumor cells. To

191 evaluate this in real-time, we performed xCelligence assays on A549 and H1299 cell

192 lines co-cultured with platelets, followed by cisplatin treatment at IC50

193 concentrations. The A549 cell line exhibited a significantly increased proliferation rate

194 as early as 24 hours post-cisplatin therapy in the presence of platelets (**Fig. 2C** and

195 **Table S1**). Specifically, at 24 hours ($p < 0.05$) and 48 hours ($p < 0.001$) post-treatment,
196 co-cultured cells exhibited enhanced proliferation compared to those without
197 platelets.

198 Similarly, the H1299 cell line showed increased proliferation under co-culture
199 conditions starting at 24 hours post-cisplatin treatment ($p < 0.05$) (**Fig. 2D** and **Table**
200 **S2**). Notably, at both 24 hours ($p < 0.05$) and 48 hours ($p < 0.01$) post-treatment, the co-
201 culture condition significantly increased the proliferation of H1299 cells (**Fig. 2D**).

202 **Figure 2.** Impact of platelets and cisplatin on apoptosis and proliferation.

203 **A)** Apoptosis levels in the A549 cell line with and without platelet co-culture following
 204 cisplatin treatment, along with representative plots Annexin V/7AAD flow cytometry

205 analysis. Cells are classified as viable (Annexin V and 7AAD negative); apoptotic
206 (Annexin V positive and 7AAD negative) or necrotic (Annexin and 7AAD double
207 positive). **B)** Apoptosis levels in the H1299 cell line alone or co-culture with platelets
208 after cisplatin treatment, with representative Annexin V/7AAD flow cytometry plots
209 showing viable, apoptotic or necrotic cell populations. **C)** Proliferation ratio in the
210 A549 cell line, either alone or co-culture with platelets, treated with cisplatin or
211 untreated. **D)** Proliferation ratio in the H1299 cell line, alone or co-culture with
212 platelets, with or without cisplatin treatment. Statistically significance between
213 cisplatin-treated cells alone and those co-culture with platelets: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$,
214 *** $p < 0.001$.

215 Abbreviations: PLT: platelets, CisPt: cisplatin, UNT: untreated.

216

217 **3- Platelets enhance colony formation of A549 and H1299 cell lines** 218 **following cisplatin treatment.**

219 Next, we evaluated the impact of platelets on the clonogenic potential of NSCLC cell
220 lines using a colony formation assay. As depicted in Fig. 3, cisplatin treatment
221 significantly reduced the colonies formed by A549 and H1299 cell lines, respectively.
222 However, when cultured with platelets, the A549 cells treated with 0.5 μM cisplatin
223 (IC5) formed significantly more colonies (82 ± 6 colonies) compared to cells treated
224 with cisplatin alone (55 ± 11 colonies) ($p < 0.05$) (**Fig. 3A**). Similar results were
225 observed at one μM cisplatin (IC10), with co-cultured A549 cells forming 41 ± 8
226 colonies versus 23 ± 9 colonies in the non-co-culture condition ($p < 0.05$) (**Fig. 3A**).
227 For the H1299 cell line, co-culture with platelets significantly increased colony
228 formation in cells treated with 0.5 μM cisplatin (165 ± 6 colonies versus 128 ± 7

229 colonies in the absence of platelets) ($p < 0.05$) (**Fig. 3B**). However, no significant
 230 differences were observed at one μM cisplatin treatment (IC10) (**Fig. 3B**).

231
 232 **Figure 3.** Influence of platelets and cisplatin on the clonogenic potential.
 233 **A)** Number of colonies per well (diameter greater than 50 μm) in the A549 cell line
 234 after cisplatin treatment, with representative images from each condition. **B)** Number
 235 of colonies per well (diameter greater than 50 μm) in the H1299 cell line after
 236 cisplatin treatment, with representative images from each condition. Significant
 237 differences between cells treated with cisplatin alone and those co-culture with
 238 platelets are indicated: * $p < 0.05$.

239 Abbreviations: PLT: platelets, CisPt: cisplatin, IC5: inhibitory concentration 5, IC10:
 240 inhibitory concentration 10, UNT: untreated.

241

242 **4- Impact of tumor cell-platelet interaction on migration capacity post-**
243 **treatment.**

244 We performed a wound-healing assay on both treated and untreated cells to evaluate
245 the effect of tumor cell-platelet interactions on migration potential. In the A549 cell
246 line, there was no significant difference in migration capacity between cells co-
247 cultured with platelets and those cultured alone under untreated conditions. However,
248 upon being treated with cisplatin, co-culture with platelets significantly enhanced the
249 migration capacity of A549 cells at 24 hours ($p < 0.05$) (**Fig. 4A**).

250 In contrast, the H1299 cell line exhibited higher migration capability, with no
251 significant differences in migration observed between the platelet co-culture and
252 control conditions, regardless of cisplatin treatment (**Fig. 4B**).

253

254

255 **Figure 4.** Influence of platelets and cisplatin on migration capability.

256 **A)** Percentage of wound closure in the A549 cell line relative to untreated control

257 following cisplatin treatment. The wound area was measured at 0, 6, 20 and 24

258 hours. Representative images depict wound closure assay after 24 hours of
259 exposure. **B)** Percentage of wound closure in the H1299 cell line relative to untreated
260 control following cisplatin treatment. The wound area was measured at 0, 6, 20 and
261 24 hours. Representative images depict wound closure assay after 24 hours of
262 exposure. Significant differences between cells treated with cisplatin alone and those
263 co-culture with platelets are indicated: * $p < 0.05$.

264 Abbreviations: PLT: platelets, CisPt: cisplatin, UNT: untreated.

265

266 **5- Platelets-induced transcriptomic changes in NSCLC cell lines.**

267 To elucidate the molecular mechanism driving the observed phenotypic changes in
268 lung cancer cells upon interaction with platelets, we performed mRNA-Seq
269 transcriptomic analysis on A549 and H1299 cells co-cultured with platelets or alone.
270 Cells were analysed after 24 and 48 hours of co-culture, followed by an additional 48-
271 hour cisplatin treatment (IC50). Differential expression analysis revealed extensive
272 transcriptomic changes across both cell lines.

273 After 24 hours of platelet co-culture, the A549 cell line exhibited 900 upregulated and
274 842 downregulated genes (**Fig. 5A, top left**), while the H1299 cell line showed 423
275 genes upregulated and 423 genes were downregulated (**Fig. 5A, bottom left**). At 48
276 hours of co-culture, similar results were observed for each cell line:

- 277 • In A549 cell line 843 genes were upregulated and 707 were downregulated (**Fig.**
278 **5A, top middle**).
- 279 • H1299 cell line presented 503 upregulated and 477 downregulated genes (**Fig.**
280 **5A, bottom middle**).

281 Following 48 hours of cisplatin treatment, the A549 line had 226 upregulated and 231
282 downregulated genes (**Fig. 5A, top right**), while H1299 had 164 upregulated and
283 200 downregulated genes (**Fig. 5A bottom right**).

284 We generated Euler diagrams to visualize overlapping differentially expressed genes
285 (DEGs) across time points and treatment conditions to explore common
286 transcriptomic alterations between both cell lines. In the A549 cell line, 830 DEGs
287 overlapped between the 24- and 48-hour co-culture conditions, while the H1299 line
288 showed 280 overlapping DEGs (**Fig. 5B, left**). Across all four conditions, including
289 time and cell line differences, only 44 genes were commonly dysregulated (**Fig. 5B,**
290 **left**).

291 When comparing pre- and post-cisplatin treatment conditions, the A549 cell line had
292 137 DEGs overlapping between the 48-hour co-culture and post-cisplatin treatment
293 conditions, while H1299 exhibited 65 overlapping DEGs (**Fig. 5B right**). Notably, no
294 genes were found to overlap across all four experimental conditions, highlighting the
295 distinct transcriptomic responses induced by platelet co-culture and cisplatin
296 treatment.

297

298 **Figure 5.** RNA-Seq analysis of A549 and H1299 cell lines in co-culture with platelets
 299 and treated with cisplatin.

300 **A top panel)** Volcano plots of differentially expressed genes (DEGs) in the A549 cell
 301 line co-culture with platelets versus alone at 24, 48 and 72 h (post-cisplatin). **A**

302 **bottom panel)** Volcano plots of DEGs in the H1299 cell line co-culture with platelets
 303 versus alone at 24, 48 and 72 hours (post-cisplatin). **B left panel)** Euler diagrams

304 showing overlapping DEGs between A549 and H1299 cell lines at 24 and 48 hours in

305 co-culture conditions. **B right panel)** Euler diagrams showing DEGs between

306 untreated and 48-hour post-cisplatin treatment conditions in both A549 and H1299
307 cell lines.

308 Abbreviations: PLT: platelets, Ctrl: control.

309

310 **6- Functional annotation analysis of differentially enriched pathways in** 311 **platelet-interacted and cisplatin-treated NSCLC cells.**

312 To better understand the molecular mechanisms induced by platelet interactions and
313 cisplatin treatment, we performed functional enrichment analysis using DAVID. We
314 focused on key KEGG pathways enriched at different time points during platelet co-
315 culture and post-cisplatin treatment.

316 In the A549 cell line, after 24 hours of co-culture with platelets, several crucial
317 pathways associated with tumor progression, proliferation, and drug resistance were
318 enriched pathways. Including the PI3K-AKT signalling pathway, TNF signalling
319 pathway, and platinum drug resistance (**Fig. 6A**). After 48 hours, we observed
320 enrichment of pathways related to the cell cycle and TNF signalling pathway (**Fig.**
321 **6A**). with the TNF pathway also remaining significantly enriched in the platelet co-
322 culture condition following cisplatin treatment (**Fig. 6A**).

323 In the H1299 cell line, after 24 hours of interaction with platelets, key pathways such
324 as platinum drug resistance, NF-kappa B signalling, and apoptosis were enriched
325 (**Fig. 6B**). By 48 hours, DNA replication and apoptosis pathways were highlighted,
326 while the Notch signalling pathway emerged as the only enriched pathway following
327 cisplatin treatment in co-culture conditions (**Fig. 6B**).

328

329

330 **Figure 6.** Functional annotation analysis of differentially enriched pathways in A549

331 and H1299 cell lines.

332 **A)** Functional enrichment analysis in the A549 cell line co-cultured with or without

333 platelets at 24, 48, and 72 hours (72 hours includes treatment with cisplatin). **B)**

334 Functional enrichment analysis in the H1299 cell line co-cultured with or without

335 platelets at 24, 48, and 72 hours (72 hours includes cisplatin treatment).

336 Abbreviations: PLT: platelets, Ctrl: control.

337

338 To validate these RNA-seq results and further explore these enriched pathways, we
339 conducted a qPCR analysis of key DEGs involved in the identified pathways across
340 both A549 and H1299 cell lines. Our findings revealed significant upregulation of
341 pivotal genes in the PI3K-AKT signalling pathway, such as *AKT1*, *PI3KCA*, and *c-*
342 *MYB*, after 24 and 48 hours of platelet co-culture and following cisplatin treatment in
343 the presence of platelets (**Fig. 7A** and **7B**).

344 We also observed upregulation of antiapoptotic genes, such as *BIRC3*in, in all
345 platelet interaction conditions. Additionally, *TGM2* was upregulated in the A549 cell
346 line at 24h and 72h and in the H1299 cell line after 24h, co-cultured with platelets
347 (**Fig. 7A** and **7B**). Simultaneously, the TNF pathway mediators *TNFRSF9* and *CREB*
348 were upregulated in A549 cells after 24 and 72 hours of platelet co-cultured,
349 respectively. This platelet-tumor cell interaction also led to increased expression of
350 *MMP-9* in the A549 cell line across all conditions (**Fig. 7A**).

351 Furthermore, the NF-kB signalling pathway, predominantly the non-canonical
352 pathway, was activated in both A549 and H1299 cells. We observed consistent
353 upregulation of *BIRC3* in all platelet interaction conditions, as well as the upregulation
354 of *RELB* in the 72-hour platelet co-culture condition and *NFKB2* in the A549 cell line
355 at 24 and 72 hours of platelet co-culture (**Fig. 7A** and **7B**).

356

357

358 **Figure 7.** Validation of differentially expressed genes by qPCR.

359 **A)** Key upregulated genes in the A549 cell line associated with PI3K-AKT, TNF,
 360 apoptosis, and NF-kappa B pathways after 24 and 48 hours of platelet co-culture and
 361 post-cisplatin treatment. **B)** Similar analysis for the H1299 cell line, highlighting
 362 upregulated genes in apoptosis and NF-kB signalling pathways. Significant
 363 differences are marked as * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$.

364 Abbreviations: PLT: platelets, UNT: untreated, CisPt: cisplatin.

365

366 DISCUSSION

367 The interaction between platelets and tumor cells has gained recognition as a crucial
 368 factor in the progression and metastasis of cancers, including NSCLC^{12,22}. Our study

369 demonstrates that platelets significantly increase the resistance of NSCLC cell lines
370 A549 and H1299 to cisplatin. When co-cultured with platelets, these cell lines
371 exhibited reduced apoptosis, increased cell proliferation, enhanced migration, and a
372 more significant clonogenic potential. Moreover, the transcriptional analysis revealed
373 several signalling pathways associated with tumor proliferation and survival, such as
374 PI3K-AKT, NF-kappa B, and TNF, were activated.

375 One key finding is that platelets confer protection to cancer cells from apoptosis, a
376 primary target of many chemotherapeutic agents. Our experiments significantly
377 reduced apoptosis in both A549 and H1299 cells co-cultured with platelets, even
378 following cisplatin treatment. This anti-apoptotic effect is likely due to direct platelet-
379 tumor interaction and biomolecule transfer, which activate survival pathways in the
380 cancer cells^{12,13,23,24}. Molecular analysis identified upregulation of essential survival
381 genes such as *BIRC3*, *c-MYB*, and *TGM2*, which were upregulated in both cell lines
382 at 24- and 48-hours post-platelet contact and after cisplatin exposure.

383 An essential aspect of our study is that while some research suggests platelets
384 enhance tumor cell proliferation²⁵, others point to their role in promoting metastasis²⁶.
385 Interestingly, we observed increased proliferation in NSCLC cells only after cisplatin
386 treatment. This suggests this may be tied to the activation of survival pathways like
387 PI3K-AKT and TNF, which are known to support cancer cell growth and survival^{27,28}.
388 Additionally, platelets enhanced the clonogenic potential of tumor cells post-cisplatin
389 treatment, demonstrating their role in cancer cell recovery and regrowth. This
390 increase in clonogenicity highlights platelets' role in shielding tumor cells from
391 chemotherapy and promoting recovery, potentially leading to tumor recurrence and
392 metastasis^{29,30}. The overexpression of genes and activation of pathways, such as
393 PI3K-AKT and NF-kB, supports these findings^{31,32}.

394 Our wound healing assays revealed that platelets also enhance the migratory
395 capacity of A549 cells, even after cisplatin treatment. However, this effect was seen
396 in H1299 cells, possibly due to their high migratory potential. Platelets facilitate
397 cancer cell migration and invasion by promoting epithelial-mesenchymal transition
398 (EMT) and activating pathways like PI3K-AKT³². In our study, EMT-related genes
399 were overexpressed in A549 cells co-cultured with platelets, highlighting the role of
400 platelets in enhancing NSCLC cell migration even in the face of chemotherapy^{29,33}.
401 These findings suggest that platelet-tumor interactions not only improve resistance to
402 chemotherapy but also activate mechanisms that contribute to cancer progression,
403 recurrence, and metastasis.

404 The transcriptomic analysis of A549 and H1299 cells co-cultured with platelets
405 revealed significant changes in gene expression, particularly highlighting alterations
406 in critical pathways such as NF-kappa B, which is known to mediate cellular stress
407 responses and contribute to chemoresistance^{34,35}. This pathway, alongside others
408 like PI3K-AKT^{32,36}, plays a critical role in cancer cell survival and the development of
409 chemoresistance, reinforcing the protective role that platelets provide within the
410 tumor microenvironment³⁷.

411 Furthermore, the functional enrichment analysis revealed that platelet interactions are
412 involved in different tumor-promoting processes, including cell cycle regulation and
413 inhibition of apoptosis. These findings suggest that platelets not only protect cancer
414 cells from the cytotoxic effects of chemotherapy but also create a supportive
415 environment that enhances tumor resilience and survival. Previous studies have
416 similarly demonstrated the influence of platelets in modulating the tumor
417 microenvironment, promoting tumor growth, and driving metastasis^{33,38}.

418 While our results offer promising insights into the protective role of platelets in
419 NSCLC, further studies are required to elucidate the precise mechanistic details of
420 platelet-tumor interactions and to validate these findings *in vivo*. Targeting these
421 interactions presents a promising therapeutic strategy to overcome chemoresistance
422 in NSCLC. However, translating this approach into clinical practice will require careful
423 consideration of platelet function in haemostasis
424 to avoid adverse effects. Future research should focus on identifying specific
425 therapeutic targets within these pathways and evaluating the potential benefits of
426 combining antiplatelet agents with chemotherapeutics to enhance treatment efficacy
427 in NSCLC.

428

429 **CONCLUSIONS**

430 Our study highlights the critical role of platelets in promoting chemoresistance,
431 survival, and metastatic potential in NSCLC cells following cisplatin treatment. Our
432 findings demonstrate that platelet-tumor interactions significantly enhance resistance
433 to apoptosis, increase cell proliferation, boost colony formation, and improve
434 migratory capacity in NSCLC cells. The activation of key signalling pathways such as
435 PI3K-AKT, NF-kappa B, and TNF drive these effects. These interactions promote
436 tumor cell survival during chemotherapy and facilitate regrowth and recovery,
437 suggesting that platelets provide a supportive microenvironment that fosters tumor
438 progression. Transcriptomic analysis further reveals extensive gene expression
439 changes that shed light on the molecular mechanisms underlying platelet-mediated
440 chemoresistance, highlighting the complexity of platelet involvement in tumor biology.

441

442 **METHODS**

443 **Platelet isolation**

444 Whole blood from healthy donors (males and females younger than 30, non-smokers
445 and non-anticoagulated) was collected into Vacutainer™ EDTA tubes (BD
446 Biosciences, Franklin Lakes, NJ, USA) and processed promptly to prevent platelet
447 activation due to prolonged storage. All blood samples were collected and processed
448 within four hours at room temperature using a swing-bucket rotor centrifuge. Initially,
449 leukocyte-rich platelet-rich plasma (L-PRP) was obtained by centrifuging at 120×g for
450 10 minutes with no break applied. L-PRP was centrifugated at 200×g for 15 minutes
451 to remove residual white blood cells and erythrocytes, yielding pure platelet-rich
452 plasma (P-PRP). Platelets were isolated from P-PRP via a final centrifugation at
453 1000×g for 10 minutes. The platelets were washed with phosphate-buffered saline
454 (PBS) containing two mM EDTA and resuspended in culture media at physiological
455 concentrations (**Fig. S1**). All experiments were conducted immediately after platelet
456 isolation to preserve platelet functionality.

457

458 **Cell culture**

459 Two human NSCLC cell lines, A549 and H1299, were used in this study. The A549
460 cell line was obtained from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC), while
461 H1299 was acquired from the Centre for Scientific Instrumentation (CIC) at the
462 University of Granada. The specific characteristics of these cell lines are detailed in
463 **Fig. S1**. Cell lines were routinely tested for mycoplasma contamination using the
464 Venor®GeM qEP (Minerva Biolabs, Berlin, Germany), and cell line authentication
465 was verified with AmpFLSTR Identifiler® Plus (Applied Biosystem, Foster City, CA,
466 USA). Both cell lines were confirmed to be mycoplasma-free and authenticated by
467 STR profiling.

468 The H1299 cell line was cultivated in RPMI 1640 (Biowest, Nuaille, France), while the
469 A549 was maintained in Dulbecco's minimal essential medium (DMEM) (BioWest).
470 Both media were supplemented with 10% Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS) (BioWest), 100
471 U/mL penicillin, and 100 mg/mL streptomycin (Sigma-Aldrich, Merck, St. Louis, MO,
472 USA). Cells were maintained at 37°C in a humidified incubator infused with 5% CO₂.

473

474 **Co-culture experiment**

475 For the co-culture experiment, tumor cells were seeded the day before platelet
476 isolation, ensuring they reached 50-60% confluence at the time of co-culture. The
477 isolated platelets were then added to the cell culture at a concentration of 1×10^5
478 platelets/ μ L.

479

480 **IC₅₀ determination assay**

481 To determine the IC₅₀ values for cisplatin, tumor cells were seeded at a density of
482 2.5×10^4 cells per well in 96-well plates and co-cultured with platelets at a predefined
483 cell-to-platelet ratio optimized for efficient interaction. The co-culture was maintained
484 for 48 hours before cisplatin was added at concentrations ranging from 0 to 256 μ M
485 (0, 0.5, 1, 2, 4, 8, 16, 32, 64, 128 and 256 μ M). Cells were treated for an additional
486 48 hours. Following the manufacturer's recommendations, cell viability was assessed
487 using a WST-1 reagent (Roche, Basel, Switzerland). Absorbance was measured at
488 450 nm using a Tecan Infinite 200 Pro microplate reader (Tecan Trading, AG,
489 Switzerland), with background absorbance corrections performed using wells
490 containing only media and reagent. Cell viability was expressed as normalized
491 absorbance relative to untreated control cells. To ensure reproducibility, multiple
492 experiments were conducted independently in triplicate.

493

494 **Apoptosis assay**

495 Apoptosis experiments were conducted using cells seeded at 1×10^5 cells per well in
496 6-well plates. After 48 hours of co-culture, the platelets were removed by washing the
497 cells twice with 1X PBS. The tumor cells were then treated with the IC50
498 concentration of cisplatin specific to each cell line. Cells were collected 24 hours
499 post-IC50 treatment for analysis. Following the manufacturer's protocol, the
500 apoptosis and cell death was quantified using the BD Pharmingen™ PE Annexin V
501 Apoptosis Detection Kit I (BD Bioscience) (**Fig. S1**). Data was acquired on a BD
502 FACSCanto™ flow cytometer employing BD FACSDiva™ software for operation
503 (BDBioscience). The collected data were analyzed using the Community Cytobank
504 platform (<https://community.cytobank.org/cytobank/login>).

505

506 **Proliferation assay**

507 The impact of platelet co-culture on cell proliferation was evaluated in real-time using
508 an xCelligence Real-Time Cell Monitoring Assay (RTCA) (xCELLigence; ACEA
509 Biosciences, San Diego, CA, USA). Tumor cells were seeded at 2×10^4 cells/well
510 RTCA plates. After 48 hours of co-culture, platelets were removed, and cells were
511 treated with the IC50 concentration of cisplatin. Cell growth was monitored over a
512 period of 120 hours, with impedance measurements recorded hourly as an indicator
513 of the Cell Index (**Fig. S1**).

514

515 **Colony assay**

516 The colony-forming ability of tumor cells following platelet co-culture was evaluated
517 by seeding 4×10^4 cells per well in 12-well plates. After the co-culture, cells were

518 detached, counted, and seeded into 6-well plates at densities of 750 cells per well for
519 A549 and 500 cells per well for H1299. Cells were then treated with the IC5 and IC10
520 concentrations of cisplatin. After ten days of growth, the colonies were fixed with
521 ethanol and stained with a crystal violet solution (**Fig. S1**). The plates were scanned,
522 and colonies were counted using Fiji software.

523

524 **Migration assay**

525 Cell migration capability was assessed using a wound-healing assay. Tumor cells
526 were seed at 1×10^4 cells per in 96-well plates. After 48 hours of co-culture, the
527 platelets were removed, and the cells were treated with the IC50 concentration of
528 cisplatin. A sterile scratch tool was used to create a wound in each well, followed by
529 washing with 1X PBS to remove debris. Fresh medium, with or without cisplatin
530 (IC50), was added (**Fig. S1**). Wound closure was monitored and photographed at the
531 start of the experiment (t0), 6 (t6), 20 6 (t20), and 24 hours (t24) using Universal Grab
532 6.3 software (Digital Cell Imaging Labs) connected to a Leica microscope equipped
533 with a TMC-1327 camera (JAI, Copenhagen, Denmark). The percentage of migration
534 was calculated using the formula: % Migration = $100 \times (\text{Wound area at t0} - \text{Wound}$
535 $\text{area at tX}) / \text{Wound area at t0}$.

536

537 **RNA extraction, library preparation, and sequencing**

538 Total RNA was extracted from cancer cells, cultured alone or co-cultured with non-
539 activated platelets using the RNA Spin Mini Kit (GE Healthcare, Chicago, IL, USA),
540 following the manufacturer's instructions. RNA concentration was quantified using the
541 Qubit® RNA BR Assay Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA), and its
542 purity and integrity were assessed with the Bioanalyzer RNA 6000 Nano kit (Agilent

543 Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA). Only samples with a minimum RNA Integrity
544 Number (RIN) of 8 were deemed suitable for sequencing.
545 Messenger RNA (mRNA) libraries were prepared using the Stranded mRNA Prep
546 Ligation Kit (Illumina, San Diego, CA, USA). Oligo(dT) magnetic beads were used to
547 purify and capture polyA mRNA molecules. The purified mRNA was then fragmented
548 and reverse-transcribed into first-strand complementary DNA (cDNA) using random
549 primers. DUTP was incorporated in place of dTTP during the second-strand cDNA
550 synthesis to ensure strand specificity. Following cDNA synthesis, 3' adenylation was
551 performed to facilitate adapter ligation. Sequencing adapters and indexes for sample
552 multiplexing were added during the subsequent PCR enrichment, where P5 and P7
553 adapter sequences were also incorporated.
554 Sequencing was performed on an Illumina NovaSeq 6000 system, using an SP flow
555 cell for paired-end sequencing (100bp x 2). Each sample achieved a minimum of 12
556 million reads, ensuring sequencing depth and coverage for comprehensive
557 transcriptomic analysis (**Fig. S2**).

558

559 **RNA-Seq analysis**

560 Raw fast files were demultiplexed and retrieved directly from the sequencer without
561 adapter sequences. To ensure data integrity, quality control of raw reads was
562 performed using FASTQC³⁹. Poor-quality reads were removed with Trimmomatic⁴⁰.
563 applying the following settings: AVGQUAL:18; CROP:94; LEADING:28;
564 SLIDINGWINDOW:5:28; HEADCROP:9, and MINLEN:50. Cleaned reads were
565 subjected to a second quality control using FASTQC and manually reviewed to
566 confirm quality improvement.

567 The clean reads were aligned to the NCBI human genome (hg38) using Spliced
568 Transcripts Alignment to a Reference (STAR) version 2.7.11a⁴¹. with gtf annotation
569 (version 110). Both paired-end and unpaired reads were aligned and merged into a
570 single BAM file per sample using Samtools⁴². BAM files were sorted by coordinates,
571 duplicates were removed, and files were indexed using Sambamba⁴³. Final aligned
572 files were assessed for quality control using "multi-bamqc" from Qualimap 2.
573 According to the report, all sample files behave alike. Qualimap 2 was also used to
574 evaluate RNA-seq alignment data ("rnaseq"), i.e., obtain the raw counts using the
575 Ensembl Gene annotation (**Fig. S2**).

576 Subsequent analyses were performed in R language⁴⁴. A single-count matrix was
577 created from the individual sample files, followed by raw count quality control using
578 NOISeq⁴⁵. Genes with a mean count below ten across all the samples were filtered
579 out to minimize noise. Technical biases related to sequence length, GC content, and
580 RNA composition were corrected using conditional quantile normalization⁴⁶.
581 combined with DESeq2 size factors estimation⁴⁷. Multivariate noise reduction was
582 performed using the ARSyN R package⁴⁸ using a three-way ANOVA model (cell line
583 × platelet presence × time) to reconstruct 0.75 of the total variability.

584 Gene expression data (Log2 normalized) was modelled gene-by-gene using the
585 *limma* R package⁴⁹ fitting a model that included up to third-order interaction effects
586 between cell line, platelet presence, time, and drug presence. Differential expression
587 was tested with empirical Bayes statistics (*limma* eBayes function), and results were
588 visualized through volcano plots, heatmaps (heatmap. two plots⁵⁰), and pathway
589 diagrams⁵¹. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. In addition,
590 Gene Set Enrichment Analysis (GSEA) was performed using the Database for

591 Annotation, Visualization, and Integrated Discovery (DAVID), using the
592 recommended EASE score ≤ 0.1 ⁵².

593

594 **qPCR analysis**

595 For quantitative PCR (qPCR) validation, one μg of total RNA was reverse transcribed
596 into cDNA using the Transcriptor First Strand cDNA Synthesis Kit (Roche). qRT-PCR
597 primers were performed with specific primers listed in Table S2 (Merck, Darmstadt,
598 Germany) using iTaq™ Universal SYBR® Green Supermix (Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA,
599 USA) on a Q6 Real-Time PCR system (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Each assay was
600 run in biological and technical triplicates, including non-template controls (NTC).
601 *GAPDH* was used as the endogenous control, and gene expression levels were
602 calculated using the $2^{-\Delta\Delta\text{Ct}}$, normalized to both the control and co-cultured cells.

603

604 **Statistics**

605 Statistical analyses and graphical visualizations were generated using GraphPad
606 Prism (version 8.0 for Windows, GraphPad software). All experiments, including
607 expression analyses and functional assays, were performed in biological and
608 technical triplicates. A t-test was applied to compare two groups in apoptosis,
609 proliferation, colony formation, and migration assays. Differences were considered
610 statistically significant when the p-value was < 0.05 .

611

612 **DATA AVAILABILITY**

613 The authors confirm that all data supporting the results included in this manuscript
614 are available in the article document or in its accompanying supplemental materials.
615 RNA-seq data that supports the findings of this study have been deposited in GEO.

616

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632

633 **AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS**

634 J.C.-H. and A.G.-D.: designed and performed the investigation, methodology, data
635 curation, formal analysis, analyzed the data, data and figure visualization, and wrote
636 the original draft; V.D.: provided resources, research supervision and visualization;
637 G.M.-N. and I.A.-P.: methodology and performed the investigation; M.P.M.:
638 performed the investigation; E.G. and J.L.H.: provided resources and research
639 supervision; C.F.: methodology, data curation, formal analysis, analyzed the data,
640 data and figure visualization; P.J.R.: provided resources and research supervision;

641 M.J.S.: provided resources, conceptualization, funding acquisition, project
642 administration, research supervision, data and figure visualization, and wrote the
643 original draft. All the authors reviewed the manuscript.

644

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